

success story

> Pilot 1: Water & Land-Use Management Regional Scale & Cross-border

Capturing Hydrological Trends by Developing Physically Based Fully Distributed Model

The intricate interactions between surface water and groundwater are paramount in shaping the hydrology of catchments, forming a complex and interconnected system. In the field of water resources management, a comprehensive understanding of catchments is crucial, and one effective approach is through the use of hydrological models. Distributed hydrological models are powerful tools capable of providing large-scale predictions and catchment insights.

However, these physically based models heavily rely on data, presenting a significant challenge for modelers. Insufficiently developed or poorly maintained local monitoring networks often lead to data scarcity. Fortunately, advancements in remote sensing technologies have revolutionized the availability of vast datasets obtained through satellite observations. These valuable observations offer insights into a wide range of parameters required for building accurate hydrological models.

In the Eiffel project's Pilot 1, we achieved a major milestone by successfully developing a model for the Aa of Weerij's catchment. Our approach incorporated a combination of global and in-situ datasets, utilizing data for digital elevation, land use, and soil texture from global sources, while relying on locally observed climatic forcing data. To ensure model accuracy, we innovated by adopting a multi-site and multi-variate calibration approach, considering streamflow, groundwater levels, and actual evapotranspiration.

The performance evaluation of our model focused on the extreme drought year of 2018. Remarkably, our model accurately captured the drought conditions during this period. With its promising results, we anticipate that our developed model will provide valuable insights for testing Nature-based solutions and designing adaptation strategies, specifically targeting water stress crises within the catchment.

This success marks a significant advancement in our ability to understand and manage catchments, paving the way for effective water resources management and sustainable solutions in the face of evolving hydrological challenges under climate change.

Useful links:

www.eiffel4climate.eu

<https://www.eiffel4climate.eu/index.php/pilots>

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